

Saving Ukrainian Cultural Heritage Online: Responsive Emergency DH at Scale

Dombrowski, Quinn

qad@stanford.edu
Stanford University, United States of America

Kijas, Anna

anna.kijas@tufts.edu
Tufts University, United States of America

Rakityanskaya, Anna

rakityan@fas.harvard.edu
Harvard University, United States of America

Wingate, Alex

alewinga@iu.edu
Indiana University, United States of America

The Russian invasion of Ukraine on February 24, 2022 created a crisis with the opportunity to build a community and take collective action in order to archive and safeguard the digital cultural heritage of Ukrainian institutions. The Saving Ukrainian Cultural Heritage Online (SUCHO) initiative was launched days later as an emergency response effort with over 1,500 volunteers co-working virtually across time zones at a scale not previously seen in DH rapid response projects. Since the start of the invasion, SUCHO has web-archived more than 5,000 websites and 50TB of data of Ukrainian cultural institutions, to prevent the data from these websites from being lost. The websites range from national archives to local museums, from 3D tours of churches to children's art centers – anywhere where people engage with Ukrainian cultural heritage – that might be at risk due to server destruction, non-payment, power outages, or other causes.

At the beginning of the project, SUCHO's focus was on publicly-available websites for Ukrainian cultural heritage institutions. Those websites depend on materials already having been digitized before the war. As noted by President of the Ukrainian Library Association Oksana Brui in a recent UNESCO meeting, only about 0.6% of the cultural heritage documents in the State Archives have been digitized to date. The urgency of digitizing cultural heritage has only grown since the war, and many institutions are beginning – or scaling up – digitization efforts. In this second phase of the initiative we are matching institutions with digitization equipment funded through our crowd-sourced budget, and creating resources for education and research, as well as to continue to boost and maintain visibility of Ukrainian cultural heritage amongst the general public. These resources include a gallery featuring a selection of curated items that were web archived from Ukrainian cultural heritage institutions' websites and a meme collection of archived visual internet memes related to the Russo-Ukrainian war.

In this poster presentation, we will provide an overview of the initiative since its launch on March 1, 2022 with a focus on several components of the initiative, including the technology and workflows used to web archive digital Ukrainian cultural heritage, im-

portance of community building, highlights from the gallery and meme collection resources for education and research, and potential ways forward in order to avoid the need for this type of an emergency response in the future. We relied mainly on the use of open-source technology with a side of proprietary software and tools when necessary. For web archiving workflows we primarily use the Webrecorder suite (Browsertrix/Browsertrix Cloud, Manual Webrecorder) developed by Ilya Kramer, in addition to the Wayback Machine from the Internet Archive, and as custom code necessary. To wrangle all of our volunteers and tasks we used Google Sheets (and later, Baserow) and Slack for communication and project management. We will provide important takeaways from the curation work of web archived items in the gallery and the meme collection. In addition, we will identify approaches and partnerships that individuals and institutions can engage with in order to take steps towards supporting proactive stewardship and preservation of digital cultural heritage collections in under-sourced parts of the globe.